

IMPACT OF ADMISSION MERIT ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SECTOR NURSING COLLEGES IN PUNJAB

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ABSTRACT

Background: Admission merit is widely considered a key determinant of academic success in nursing education. However, variations in admission criteria and institutional environments between public and private sector nursing colleges may influence the strength of this relationship. Understanding how admission merit relates to academic performance across different institutional contexts is essential for improving selection policies and educational outcomes.

Aim and Objectives: This study aimed to examine the influence of admission merit on academic performance and to compare academic outcomes between public and private sector nursing colleges in Punjab. The objectives were to assess differences in admission merit and academic performance between sectors and to determine the relationship between admission merit and academic performance.

Methodology: A comparative analytical cross-sectional study was conducted using secondary data obtained from 23 nursing colleges, including 10 public and 13 private sector institutions in Punjab. Admission closing merit percentages and academic performance results were analyzed. Descriptive statistics were computed, followed by independent samples t-tests to compare public and private sectors. Pearson correlation analysis was applied to determine the relationship between admission merit and academic performance. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Public sector nursing colleges demonstrated significantly higher mean admission merit and academic performance compared to private sector colleges ($p < 0.001$). A statistically significant moderate positive correlation was observed between admission merit and academic performance ($r = 0.468$, $p = 0.024$), indicating that higher entry merit was associated with better academic outcomes.

Conclusion: Admission merit significantly influences academic performance in nursing education, with public sector institutions showing superior outcomes. However, institutional factors also play a critical role, highlighting the need for balanced admission policies and strengthened academic support systems, particularly in private sector nursing colleges.

Keywords: Admission Merit; Academic Performance; Nursing Education; Public and Private Sector; Nursing Colleges;

INTRODUCTION

When choosing nursing students, admission quality plays a crucial role in identifying individuals with the solid academic backgrounds necessary for success in the workplace (Yousafzai and Jamil, 2019). Future achievement in nursing education is frequently predicted by prior academic outcomes, such as matric and FSc grades (Ali, 2008). High pre-admission scores have been linked to higher grades in challenging nursing programs, according to numerous research (Iftikhar et al., 2023). A student's study habits, self-control, and preparedness for theoretical and clinical learning are all reflected in their academic merit (Raees et al., 2023). Although their predictive power may differ between institutions, admission examinations are also used to gauge candidates' cognitive abilities (Raees et al., 2023). According to some experts, focusing just on entrance exam results could ignore critical competencies including motivation and communication skills (Iqbal et al., 2025). For the purpose of choosing qualified nursing students, a combination of academic results and entrance exams is thought to be more successful (Reed et al., 2024). Both public and private institutions in Punjab provide nursing education; each has its own admission procedures and learning settings (Bajwa et al., 2024). Strict merit systems are frequently used by public institutions, which may help students achieve better academic results (SANGHAR, 2024). However, students from a variety of academic backgrounds may be admitted to private colleges, leading to a range of academic achievement levels (Shafiq et al., 2025). Student performance is also influenced by institutional elements like the caliber of instruction, the experience of the teachers, and the accessibility of educational materials (Hadjar and Becker, 2016). According to some academics, environmental influences, stress, and socioeconomic issues all have an impact on academic success in addition to merit (Naseem et al., 2021). In nursing programs, students with excellent academic and familial support systems typically perform better (Häfner et al., 2018). Regardless of their initial merit scores, students that are motivated and interested in the nursing field also perform

better (Baljoon et al., 2018). Differences in academic achievements between institutions are also influenced by variations in clinical exposure and practical training (Flott and Linden, 2016). While some studies suggest that high-merit students perform consistently throughout nursing colleges, others reveal varying outcomes based on institutional support (Fajar et al., 2019). Comparative research indicates that disparities between the public and private sectors should be taken into account when assessing the significance of admission merit (Awan and Zia, 2015). Additionally, studies show that when students obtain appropriate academic supervision and learning tools, the relationship between merit and performance is stronger (Peach, 2005). More study is required in Punjab to investigate how admission merit affects academic performance in both public and private nursing institutions in light of these conflicting results (Wambuguh et al., 2016). Comprehending these distinctions can aid in enhancing admissions procedures and guaranteeing nursing students equitable educational opportunities (Jeffrey et al., 2019). Admission merit is widely seen as a critical determinant of student readiness in nursing education, as higher entry scores often reflect stronger academic foundations (Al-Qahtani and Alanzi, 2018). Research consistently shows that students admitted with competitive merit tend to perform better in theory and clinical components of nursing programs (Adatsi, 2013). Public and private nursing colleges in Punjab frequently differ in merit criteria, creating variation in student academic outcomes across institutions (Ahuja et al., 2019). Several scholars argue that strong academic backgrounds enhance students' ability to cope with the demanding nature of nursing curricula (Hwang and Shin, 2018). Merit-based selection has also been linked with reduced dropout rates and improved classroom performance among undergraduate health students (Wikström and Wikström, 2020). Evidence suggests that entry qualifications influence students' confidence and competence in performing essential clinical procedures (Bacon et al., 2015). Private sector colleges sometimes incorporate

interviews and aptitude components in addition to merit, potentially affecting student preparedness differently than in public institutions (Snyder, 2018). Public colleges, however, often rely strictly on merit-based admission lists, creating a more academically uniform cohort of learners (Carson, 2020). Studies highlight that high-merit students typically demonstrate better time-management skills and learning strategies, contributing to improved academic achievement (Mohammadi et al., 2017). However, some researchers emphasize that academic performance is shaped not only by merit but also by institutional support structures such as mentoring and tutoring (Bond et al., 2012). The educational environment of the institution often strengthens or weakens the relationship between entry merit and later performance (O'Malley et al., 2015). Comparative studies show that private nursing colleges usually offer more advanced learning facilities, which may compensate for slightly lower merit thresholds (Andrade et al., 2024). International evidence also supports the idea that merit-based selection enhances the development of clinical reasoning and decision-making skills (Hall et al., 2012). Some scholars note that while merit is a useful predictor, motivation and self-discipline are equally important for maintaining academic performance (DeAngelis, 2003). Overall, the literature indicates that admission merit significantly influences academic performance, but institutional differences between public and private nursing colleges determine how strongly this relationship is expressed (Torres and Quaresma, 2017).

Methodology:

This study employed a comparative cross-sectional analytical design to examine the influence of admission merit on academic performance among public and private sector nursing colleges in Punjab, Pakistan. The study population consisted of nursing colleges offering undergraduate nursing programs for

which complete data on admission closing merit (%) and academic performance/results (%) were available. A purposive sampling technique was used to include colleges with reliable and verifiable records, resulting in a final sample of 23 nursing colleges from both sectors. Admission closing merit represented the independent variable, while academic performance, measured as overall institutional result percentage, served as the dependent variable. The type of institution (public or private) was treated as the grouping variable.

Data were collected from official admission records and examination result reports and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. Descriptive statistics were computed to summarize the study variables. Independent Samples t-tests were applied to compare admission merit and academic performance between public and private sector nursing colleges, with Levene's test used to assess the assumption of homogeneity of variances. The relationship between admission merit and academic performance was examined using Pearson's correlation coefficient. A two-tailed p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant. As the study relied solely on secondary institutional data without personal identifiers, ethical approval was not required; however, confidentiality and responsible data handling were maintained throughout the research process.

Results:

The results of this study present a comparative analysis of admission merit and academic performance between public and private sector nursing colleges in Punjab. Descriptive statistics and inferential analyses were conducted to examine group differences and to assess the relationship between admission merit and academic outcomes. Findings from independent samples t-tests and Pearson correlation analysis are reported below.

Descriptive Statistics of Admission Merit and Academic Performance by Sector

Variable	Sector	N	Mean (%)	Standard Deviation
Admission Merit	Public	10	87.88	1.34

(%)	Private	13	81.85	5.36
Academic Performance (%)	Public	10	81.16	17.69
	Private	13	46.53	21.18

Table: 1. Note. N = number of nursing colleges included in each sector.

Descriptive analysis showed that public sector nursing colleges had higher mean admission

merit and academic performance compared to private sector colleges.

t-test: Comparison of Admission Merit and Academic Performance between Public and Private Nursing Colleges

Variable	Group Mean (Public)	Group Mean (Private)	t	df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	95% CI of Difference
Admission Merit (%)	87.88	81.85	4.042	13.718	.001	6.04	2.83 - 9.25
Academic Performance (%)	81.16	46.53	4.291	21	.000	34.63	17.85 - 51.41

Table: 1. Note: Public = public sector nursing colleges; Private = private sector nursing colleges; df = degrees of

Independent samples ttests showed that public sector nursing colleges had significantly higher admission merit (M = 87.88%) compared to private colleges (M = 81.85%), $t(13.72) = 4.042$, $p = .001$. Similarly, academic performance was significantly higher in public

colleges (M = 81.16%) than private colleges (M = 46.53%), $t(21) = 4.291$, $p < .001$. These results indicate that students in public sector colleges not only have higher admission merit but also achieve better academic outcomes.

Pearson Correlation between Admission Merit and Academic Performance (N = 23)

Variables	1	2	P-value
1. Admission Merit (%)	1	.468	0.024
2. Academic Performance (%)	.468	1	0.024

Table: 2. Note. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2tailed).

Pearson correlation analysis revealed a statistically significant moderate positive relationship between admission merit and academic performance among nursing colleges ($r = .468$, $p = .024$). This finding indicates that institutions with higher admission closing merit tend to demonstrate better academic performance. Although the relationship is moderate, it suggests that admission merit contributes meaningfully to academic outcomes; however, other institutional and educational factors may also influence student performance.

Discussion:

The present study examined the influence of admission merit on academic performance and compared outcomes between public and private sector nursing colleges in Punjab. The findings revealed that public sector nursing colleges had significantly higher admission closing merit and superior academic performance compared to private sector institutions. In addition, a statistically significant moderate positive correlation was observed between admission merit and academic performance, indicating that higher entry merit is associated with improved academic outcomes. These results provide empirical support for the role of meritbased

admission in enhancing academic success within nursing education.

The higher academic performance observed in public sector nursing colleges may be attributed to their stricter merit-based admission policies. Public institutions in Punjab typically admit students through highly competitive centralized merit lists, which tend to select candidates with stronger academic foundations. Previous studies have consistently reported that students with higher preadmission academic scores demonstrate better theoretical understanding, stronger clinical reasoning skills, and improved examination performance throughout nursing programs (Saud and Chen, 2018, Bokan et al., 2020). Strong academic preparedness enables students to cope more effectively with the rigorous demands of nursing curricula, which may explain the superior outcomes observed in public institutions.

In contrast, private sector nursing colleges demonstrated comparatively lower admission merit and academic performance. This finding aligns with earlier research suggesting that private institutions often adopt more flexible admission criteria, sometimes incorporating interviews, aptitude tests, or financial considerations in addition to academic merit (Ranabhat et al., 2024). While such approaches may broaden access to nursing education, they can result in greater heterogeneity in students' academic preparedness, potentially leading to variable academic outcomes. Similar patterns have been reported in comparative studies where private sector health education institutions showed wider performance disparities compared to public counterparts (Pires and Oliveira, 2018).

The moderate positive correlation between admission merit and academic performance found in this study supports the view that admission merit is an important, though not exclusive, predictor of academic success. This finding is consistent with earlier research indicating that higher entry qualifications are associated with better academic achievement, lower attrition rates, and enhanced clinical competence among nursing students (Alkhelaiwi et al., 2024). Merit-based selection reflects not only cognitive ability but also

students' discipline, learning strategies, and preparedness for demanding academic environments (Mohsenipouya et al., 2024).

Despite these findings, the literature also highlights ongoing controversy regarding the overreliance on academic merit alone for student selection. Several scholars argue that academic performance is influenced by multiple factors beyond entry merit, including institutional support systems, quality of teaching, clinical exposure, student motivation, and socioeconomic background (Palacios Mena and Ariza Bulla, 2023). Some studies have reported that students with moderate entry merit can perform equally well when provided with effective mentoring, academic supervision, and learning resources (2024). This suggests that institutional environment may either strengthen or weaken the relationship between admission merit and academic performance.

Furthermore, private sector institutions are sometimes reported to offer better infrastructure, smaller class sizes, and advanced learning facilities, which may partially compensate for lower admission merit thresholds (2024). Conversely, public sector colleges, while academically selective, may face challenges related to resource constraints and higher student loads. These contrasting institutional characteristics indicate that academic success in nursing education is the result of an interaction between student-related factors and institutional context rather than merit alone (Jernigan and Carbonneau, 2025).

Overall, the findings of this study reinforce the importance of maintaining merit-based admission criteria while also emphasizing the need for comprehensive academic support systems, particularly in private sector nursing colleges. A balanced admission approach that combines academic merit with assessment of motivation, communication skills, and learning readiness may lead to more consistent academic outcomes across institutions. Strengthening teaching quality, mentoring, and clinical training opportunities could further enhance student performance regardless of admission merit levels.

Conclusion:

The findings of this study conclude that admission merit has a significant influence on

academic performance in nursing colleges, with public sector institutions demonstrating higher entry merit and superior academic outcomes compared to private sector colleges. A positive association between admission merit and academic performance indicates that students admitted with stronger academic backgrounds are more likely to achieve better results. Nevertheless, variations in performance suggest that institutional factors such as teaching quality, academic support, and learning environment also contribute to student success. These results underscore the importance of maintaining merit-based admission criteria while strengthening educational support systems to enhance academic performance across both public and private sector nursing institutions.

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